

DISASTER MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ERA: THE POWER OF SOCIAL MEDIA ENGAGEMENT

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Abstract:

Social media has become a pivotal tool in disaster management, offering platforms for rapid information dissemination, public engagement, and coordination of relief efforts. This study explores how social media contributes to public awareness and preparedness before disasters and its effectiveness in mobilizing volunteers and donations afterward. Using a descriptive research design, primary data were collected from 100 respondents representing students, working professionals, and the general public through structured questionnaires. The study examines demographic variations in social media usage, the level of disaster preparedness promoted through online campaigns, and the post-disaster participation facilitated via social platforms. Findings highlight the influence of digital literacy, access, and trust on social media's effectiveness, while also pointing to challenges such as misinformation and unequal access. Insights from this research provide a basis for improving social media strategies to enhance community resilience and disaster response across diverse population groups.

Keywords: Social media, disaster management, public awareness, disaster preparedness, volunteer mobilization, donations, demographic differences, digital literacy, misinformation.

Introduction:

The word Society traces its etymology from the Latin word Socius, which means Companionship. Human beings through developing their societal structure, also develop a collective consciousness, which is a cradle of shared or common knowledge within a society. Disaster communication has undergone a shift along with the development of media. The internet, which began to be used widely in the early 2000s, changed how information was collected and distributed. In addition, new media and social media are rapidly growing, especially with the ease of access provided by smartphones and tablets. Finally, internet-based media has become a communication medium that is widely used and an essential component of most people's lives. This platform offers various features to create message content and build a comfortable socialization space for its users. Disaster happens unexpectedly albeit it is a natural disaster or a man-made disaster. It cause severe breakdown to a functioned community due to losses that exceed the community's capability to cope (WHO, 2014). More than that, communication that is expected to be stable and operated as it is intended often breakdown during disaster. In the new era where

social media has gained its popularity, the technology also has expand its usefulness in many areas including in disaster management. Now, social media is of particular interest in disaster management due to its advantages over the traditional communication. Communication is a core component of disaster planning, response, and recovery. Effective disaster communication may prevent a disaster or lessen its impact, whereas ineffective disaster communication may cause a disaster or make its effects worse. This diminished communication capacity occurs at a time when uncer-tainty and threat are great, producing a high demand for information. Consequently, developing effective disaster communication processes and systems should be a priority for governments, organisations, communities, and citizens. Emerging and evolving communication technologies, such as social media, offer the possibility of improved disaster communication, as these technologies have the potential for increased information capacity, dependability, and interactivity. The togetherness of the past enabled them to survive difficult times, including natural calamities and disasters. Technology was the later addition to the life of human beings. But even before that man lived in

coalition and interdependence. Technology and its inventions played a huge role in both transforming and developing former modes of communication and companionship.

Review of Literature :

Krisanthi Seneviratne et al.(2024)¹ conducted an empirical study on the Studies on social media and disaster management have mainly focused on the adaptation, application, and use of social media in each stage of disaster management. With the widespread availability and use of social media, the effective utilisation of social media in disaster management is impeded by various challenges but not yet comprehensively researched. This study adopts a systematic literature review to present and analyse the challenges and strategies for using social media in disaster management. The findings revealed four key challenges to its users: the spread of misinformation; insufficient human resources to manage social media use; the lack of trust in information and authorities; and the poor information quality and content of messages. This study identified several strategies to overcome challenges, which can be classified into three sectors of the social media community: individuals, organisations, and social media companies. Furthermore, this study provides insight into the current status of knowledge and identifies the research gaps around social media in disaster management for future research.

Turgut Acikara et al.(2023)² made a detailed study on the Disasters are sudden and catastrophic events with fatal consequences. Time-sensitive information collection from disaster zones is crucial for improved and data-driven disaster response. However, information collection from disaster zones in a prompt way is not easy or even possible. Human-centric information provided by citizen sensors through social media platforms create an opportunity for prompt information collection from disaster zones. There is, nevertheless, limited scholarly work that provides a comprehensive review on the potential of social media analytics for disaster response. This study utilizes a systematic literature review with PRISMA protocol to investigate the potential of social media analytics for enhanced disaster response. The findings inform authorities' decision-making processes as near-real time

disaster response management depending on social media analytics is a critical element of securing sustainable cities and communities.

R.I Ogie et al.(2022)³ in the article examined that the studies on the role of social media in disaster management have so far focused mainly on early phases of the disaster response process. Published evidence regarding the scope and effectiveness of social media use in the recovery phase is limited but promising. There is currently no study that provides a comprehensive picture of the current research landscape that can inform different groups who need to capitalise on social media for disaster recovery. The present study aims to address this research gap by conducting a systematic literature review of social media use in disaster recovery. Importantly, the paper identifies and summarises research findings relating to social media use in various aspects of disaster recovery, including donations and financial support, solidarity and social cohesion, post-disaster reconstruction and infrastructure services, socioeconomic and physical wellbeing, information support, mental health and emotional support, and business & economic activities.

Statement of the Problem:

In recent years, social media has emerged as a significant communication tool during disasters, enabling rapid dissemination of information, public awareness, and coordination of relief efforts. Government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and individuals increasingly use social media platforms to share warnings, preparedness measures, and post-disaster relief information. Despite its widespread use, there is limited empirical evidence on how effectively social media creates public awareness and preparedness before disasters and how successfully it mobilizes volunteers and donations after disasters. Furthermore, demographic differences in access, usage, and trust in social media may influence its effectiveness in disaster management. The presence of misinformation, unequal access, and varying levels of digital literacy further complicate the use of social media during emergencies. Therefore, there is a need to systematically examine the role of social media in disaster management, focusing on public awareness, preparedness, volunteer mobilization,

and donation efforts across different demographic groups.

Objectives of the study:

- To study the demographic profile of respondents using social media in disaster management.
- To assess public awareness and readiness created through social media campaigns before disasters
- To assess the role of social media in mobilizing volunteers and donations after disasters.

Research methodology:

This study adopts a descriptive research design to examine the demographic profile of respondents, the role of social media in creating public awareness and preparedness before disasters, and its effectiveness in mobilizing volunteers and donations after disasters. Primary data was collected from 100 respondents using a structured questionnaire administered through Google Forms

and face-to-face interactions. The respondents included students, working professionals, and members of the general public to ensure a diverse and representative sample. The questionnaire consisted of demographic questions, Likert-scale statements, and ranking-based questions related to disaster awareness, preparedness, and post-disaster mobilization through social media. Secondary data was collected from textbooks, academic journals, government and disaster management reports, official websites, research articles, and online sources to support and strengthen the study. The respondents were selected using simple random sampling, based on their availability and willingness to participate in the survey. The data collection period spanned from November 2025 to February 2026. The study is limited to respondents who actively use social media, and the findings are based on self-reported data, which may be influenced by personal perceptions and experiences. Therefore, the results may involve a degree of subjectivity and may not be generalizable to all populations.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

**TABLE NO: 1
 Personal Outline of The Respondent**

Personal Profile	Particular	No.of Respondents	Percent
Gender	Male	58	58
	Female	42	42
Age	18-28	28	28
	19-38	32	32
	39-50	19	19
	Above 50	21	21
Educational Qualification	No Formal Education	15	15
	Secondary	20	20
	Higher Secondary	25	25
	Undergraduate	26	26
	Postgraduate	14	14
Occupational Status	Unemployed	18	18
	Housewife	17	17
	Student	20	20
	Entrepreneur	15	15
	Private employee	18	18
	Government employee	12	12
	Upto Rs. 50,000	42	42

Monthly Income of the family	Rs.50,001 to Rs.1,00,000	28	28
	Rs.1,00,001 to Rs.1,50,000	22	22
	Above Rs. 1,50,000	8	8
Frequency of Social Media Use	Less than 1 hour/day	5	5
	1-3 hours/day	30	30
	3-5 hours/day	28	28
	More than 5 hours/day	37	37

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

From the above table, Minority of the respondents are female (42%). The least number of the respondents are aged between 39-50 (19%) and their educational qualification is post graduate (14%) and their occupational status is government employee (12%) and their frequency of social media usage for less than 1 hour/day is (5%).

TABLE NO: 2
Social Media Platforms Used

S.No	Social Media Platforms Used	Number	Percentage
1	Facebook	20	20
2	Instagram	30	30
3	Twitter / X	10	10
4	WhatsApp	25	25
6	YouTube	15	15
	Total	100	100

Source : Primary Data

The findings reveals that Instagram (30%) is the most preferred social media platform, followed by WhatsApp (25%) and Facebook (20%). YouTube has moderate usage of (15%), while Twitter/X (10%) is the least used among the respondents.

CHART NO: 1
Social Media Platforms Used

Table No 3
Statement of social media campaigns before disasters

S.No	Statement	SA	A	N	D	SD	Mean	Total
		5	4	3	2	1		
1	Government or official agency posts on social media are useful for disaster awareness.	38	42	12	6	2	100	4.08
		190	168	36	12	2	408	
2	Social media provides timely information before the occurrence of a disaster.	40	41	10	7	2	100	4.10
		200	164	30	14	2	410	
3	Social media messages motivate me to prepare in advance for disasters.	35	40	15	7	3	100	3.97
		175	160	45	14	3	397	
4	I feel more confident about handling a disaster due to information received on social media.	32	44	14	8	2	100	3.96
		160	176	42	16	2	396	
5	Social media helps me stay alert during disaster warning periods.	45	38	9	6	2	100	4.18
		225	152	27	12	2	418	
6	I trust disaster-related information shared on social media.	28	42	18	9	3	100	3.83
		140	168	54	18	3	383	
7	Visual content (videos, infographics) on social media improves my understanding of disaster preparedness.	41	39	11	6	3	100	4.09
		205	156	33	12	3	409	
8	Social media is more effective than traditional media (TV, radio, newspapers) for disaster awareness.	36	40	14	7	3	100	3.99
		180	160	42	14	3	399	

(SA – Strongly Agree, A – Agree, N – Neutral, D – Disagree, SD – Strongly Disagree)

Interpretation

It can be included from the above table that the level of awareness about the disaster management among the respondents. Overall the very high awareness for the Social media helps me stay alert during disaster warning periods (4.18), Social media provides timely information before the occurrence of a disaster (4.10), Visual content (videos, infographics) on social media improves my understanding of disaster preparedness(4.09),

Government or official agency posts on social media are useful for disaster awareness(4.08), Social media is more effective than traditional media (TV, radio, newspapers) for disaster awareness (3.99), Social media messages motivate me to prepare in advance for disasters.(3.97), I feel more confident about handling a disaster due to information received on social media (3.96), I trust disaster-related information shared on social media (3.83).

TABLE NO: 4
Friedman Ranking Analysis- Role of Social Media in Mobilizing Volunteers and Donations after Disasters

S.No	Role of Social Media	Mean Rank	Rank
1	Official government or disaster management agency posts	4.03	2
2	Posts shared by NGOs and relief organizations	4.11	5
3	Influencer or celebrity appeals	4.58	10
4	Posts shared by friends or family	4.50	9
5	Images and videos showing disaster impact	4.05	3
6	Emergency fundraising links	4.33	7

7	Visual evidence (photos/videos of affected areas)	4.07	4
8	Personal stories of disaster victims	4.41	8
9	Transparent updates on fund usage	4.26	6
10	Live updates from disaster locations	4.01	1

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

The table shows that respondents strongly agree on the important role of social media in disaster management. The majority of the respondents results in live updates from disaster locations (4.01), followed by Official government or disaster management agency posts (4.03), Images and videos showing disaster impact (4.05), Visual evidence (photos/videos of affected areas) (4.07), Posts shared by NGOs and relief organizations (4.11), Transparent updates on fund usage(4.26), Emergency fundraising links(4.33), Personal stories of disaster victims(4.41), Posts shared by friends or family(4.50), Influencer or celebrity appeals (4.58).

Suggestion:

Disaster management strategies should integrate technology and digital platforms, especially social media, to ensure faster dissemination of accurate information during emergencies. Government agencies must strengthen community participation and awareness programs so that people are better prepared to respond to disasters at the local level. There is a need for better coordination among central, state, and local authorities to improve efficiency in disaster preparedness, response, and recovery. New media and social media can help communities organize better, such as bringing volunteers together, coordinating help, and sharing needs and resources among affected people. Rather than limiting their use to emergency situations alone, these platforms can play a proactive role in educating communities, reducing risks, and supporting long-term rehabilitation efforts. The research also highlights the importance of ensuring that information shared through social media is accurate, reliable, and verified, as misinformation during disasters can create panic and reduce public trust. By sharing relevant warnings, situational updates, and emergency guidance, social media can help communities respond more effectively before,

during, and after a disaster. The findings also emphasize that social media facilitates quick dissemination of information without the delays often seen in traditional systems, helping to connect stakeholders, responders, and affected individuals. Additionally, the framework proposed in the study encourages disaster managers and organizations to maximize social media's potential by using it as both a data collection source and a means to mobilize support, volunteers, and resources during recovery.

Conclusion:

The study concludes that social media has emerged as a significant tool in disaster management, providing a platform for rapid information dissemination, public engagement, and community support. It highlights that while official agencies and NGOs can leverage these platforms for efficient coordination and relief activities, challenges such as misinformation and unequal access need to be addressed. The research emphasizes the importance of integrating social media into formal disaster management strategies, alongside traditional communication methods, to ensure timely, accurate, and effective responses. Overall, when used responsibly and strategically, social media can enhance preparedness, facilitate real-time response, and support recovery efforts, making it a valuable component of modern disaster mitigation efforts. It facilitates rapid information dissemination, improves coordination among authorities, volunteers, and affected communities, and helps raise awareness on preparedness and response measures. Social platforms also support recovery efforts by enabling resource mobilization, volunteer engagement, and reconnecting affected individuals. Despite its advantages, careful management is necessary to prevent misinformation and ensure the accuracy of shared content. When strategically integrated into disaster management frameworks, social media can

significantly enhance efficiency, responsiveness, and community involvement during emergencies.

Reference:

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